

Mini-Review

Role of Vitamins D and A in Immune System of Multiple Sclerosis Patients: An Updated Mini-Review

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ABSTRACT

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory demyelinating and degenerative disease of the central nervous system (CNS) and also it is the most common disabling neurological disorder in youth and in middle aged people. Some environmental factors like vitamins are important because they can have notable role in pathogenesis of MS and can be engaged as treatment simply. Role of vitamin D is critical in MS and deficiency of vitamin D is clear in MS patients. This deficiency indicates increasing distribution of MS prevalence with increasing latitude gradient that exists between northern to southern hemispheres. Also role of other vitamins in MS pathogenesis is important. In this review, we aimed to shed a light on the role of vitamins in pathogenesis and recovery of MS disease.

Keywords: Multiple Sclerosis, Vitamin D, Vitamin A, Immune System.

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory demyelinating and degenerative disease of the central nervous system (CNS) and also it is the most common disabling neurological disorder in youth and in middle aged people (1). Prevalence of MS is varies in different countries it divided in high (30/100 000) intermediate (5-25/100 000) and low (less than 5/100 000) risk areas (2, 3). More than 2.1 million individuals are suffering from MS worldwide and this prevalence is increasing in most regions of world (4, 5). Although Charcot described Multiple Sclerosis (MS) disease for the first time approximately 150 years ago but until today there is no cure for MS (6). MS subdivided into different subtypes: Relapsing Remitting Multiple Sclerosis (RRMS); almost 85% of patient have this type, that characterized by episodes of relapsing and remitting in following, Secondary Progressive Multiple

Sclerosis; 70 to 80 percent of patients with RRMS transform to this type after 20-25 years old which characterized with chronic progression. In this type progression doesn't begin from beginning time of diagnosing, Primary Progressive Multiple Sclerosis (PPMS); that is recognized with chronic progression from beginning time of disease and without clinical remission (7). Although MS etiology is unknown but like most other autoimmune disease, environmental and genetic factors are involved in MS etiology. Yet there is no definite cause for MS disease but some genetic and environmental factors proposed (8). Genetic aspect of MS disease described when family studies was done (performed). The families with approximately 20 to 30 percent recurrence rate of MS, also with increasing risk of MS between 10 to 12 folds in first and three folds in second degree relatives (9). Rarity of MS occurrence in some ethnics such as Turkmen,

Uzbeks, Kazakhs, and conversely high occurrence of MS in ethnics like Sardinians, Palestinians, Parsis and high concordance rate of monozygotic twins in compared with dizygotic twins indicate a notable genetic role in susceptibility to MS. Some genetic factors which can susceptible individuals to MS are interleukin 7 receptor alpha chain, interleukin 2 receptor alpha chain, CLEC16A, CD 58, CD 226 and etc. (10). The first defined gene which can susceptible individuals to MS disease is HLA DRB1501 (11), it is strongest gene that can susceptible individuals more than 4 fold to MS. Several proposed environmental factors are vitamin D, sunlight exposure, virus infections, and geographical distribution (12, 13). Some environmental factors like vitamins are important because they can have notable role in pathogenesis of MS and can engaged as treatment simply. Role of vitamin D is critical in MS and deficiency of vitamin D is clear in MS patients. This deficiency indicates increasing distribution of MS prevalence with increasing latitude gradient that exists between northern to southern hemispheres. Also role of other vitamins in MS pathogenesis is important. In this review we aimed to clear role of vitamins in pathogenesis and recovery of MS disease.

Vitamin A

Vitamin A like vitamin D is soluble fat vitamin, which found in animal products as retinyl esters and in fruits in forms of carotenoids. Vitamin A has some functions in body, including: effect on vision, reproduction, morphogenesis, growth and also on immune system. Reports of serum level of vitamin A in serum of MS patients are controversial (14). Runia et al. (15) performed a study that concluded lower serum level of vitamin A in serum of MS patients in comparing with control group however this reducing in serum level of vitamin A in MS patients was not significant. In the other hand Besler et al. (16) performed a study which concluded similar serum level of vitamin A in MS patients in comparing with control group. However serum level of retinol was lower in MS patients in comparing with other neurological patients. Some functions of vitamin A on immune system including: increasing tolerance, effect on adaptive and innate immune system, regulation of gene expression with RXR receptor which located on DNA, promoting remyelination by RXR γ receptors, promoting Th₂ differentiation and simultaneously inhibiting Th₁ differentiation, promoting development of Treg and regulation of interleukin 10 secretion, increasing the function and number of Th₂. Also vitamin A like vitamin D can increase anti-inflammatory cytokines and decrease inflammatory cytokines (17). "

Therapeutic strategies which lead to shift from Th₁ to Th₂ and Th₁₇ to regulatory T cell are beneficial for treatment of MS". With addition to after mentioned vitamin A can engage as a supplement for MS patients, like some immune mediated diseases. Vitamin A has been used for treatment of psoriasis and contact dermatitis, but rapid absorption, slow clearance and long half-life of vitamin A can make some problems in people who treated with vitamin A supplement (18).

Vitamin D

Vitamin D is a steroid hormone. It discovered by Dr. Elmer McCollum in 1921 (19). Initially 7-dehydrocholesterol changes to vitamin D₃ or during exposure of sunlight under the skin. Then vitamin D₃ converts to 25 hydroxy vitamin D with 25 hydroxylase. This chemical change occurs in liver mainly. Active form of vitamin D in body is 1, 25 dehydroxy vitamin D. Major circulating form of vitamin D is 25 hydroxyl and its last metabolism before active form of vitamin D (20). For the first time relationship between pattern of MS prevalence and latitude recognized by Davenport in 1921. Prevalence of MS is rare in equator and it is notably increased in temperate regions. This pattern of MS linked to sun exposure in 1960s. So with increasing latitude and MS prevalence and decreasing sun exposure, it suggested the relationship between MS risk and vitamin D (21). Vitamin D is one of the most important factors of environmental aspect of MS etiology (21). One hypothesis is exerting protective effect on individuals in tropic regions with increasing level of vitamin D. The best evidence for relationship between MS and vitamin D performed on seven million soldiers. After measuring Serum level of vitamin D, the result was low prevalence of MS among soldiers with high level of vitamin D in the time of recruitment (22). In addition to MS vitamin D insufficiency is associated with other autoimmune disease, such as rheumatoid arthritis and systemic lupus erythematosus (23). Serum level of calcifediol is lower during relapses than remission time (12). Vitamin D receptor express on microglia and activated monocyte cells also it express on T and B cells (24). Existing of vitamin D receptor on immune cells suggest a regulatory function on immune system because with activation of vitamin D receptor, it can change transcription, proliferation and differentiation of immune cells and when VDR activate with hormonal vitamin D, it stimulates a shift from responses of proinflammatory Th₁ to responses of anti-inflammatory Th₂ (25). So vitamin D plays an anti-inflammatory and immune-modulatory role in body (26). Also vitamin D supplementation in

addition to anti-inflammatory has neuro-protective effect on different type of MS also it can reduce gadolinium enhancing lesions (21, 27). High level of calcifediol and function of T regulatory cells are associated and 1, 25 (OH)₂ D₃ increase regulatory T cells. As we know clinical features of MS is associated with increasing level of proinflammatory cytokines like TNF α , interleukin 2 and interferon γ and decreasing level of anti-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin 13 and TGF β 1. 1,25 hydroxy vitamin D₃ reduce production of proinflammatory cytokines and vitamin D supplement decreases TGF β 1 in serum of patients with MS (28). Also 1, 25 (OH)₂ D reduces production of interferon γ and tumor necrosis alpha it increases in interleukin 4, 5 and 10 (28). Stimulating of dendritic cells with vitamin D, induce T cell apoptosis so it can prevent from uncontrolled proliferation through apoptosis induction (29). Also vitamin D and expanded disability status scale (EDSS) are associated however this association is different among researchers. Some researchers like Smolder et al. in their study, concluded lower level of vitamin D and higher level of EDSS are associated in the other hand some studies did not found any relationship between EDSS and vitamin D (30). Also vitamin D has negatively correlation with relapse rate and with depression (31). So according to mentioned in above, role of vitamin D is critical in clinical features of MS patients and it seems vitamin D is most important among other vitamins for this disease.

Conflict of interest

None.

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